

Technologies for Clarifying Educational Goals and Converting them into Assignments In Educational Activities that Develop Students ' Intellectual Abilities

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 4 Oct 2024; **Accepted:** 10 Nov 2024; **Published:** 05 Dec 2024

Abstract: This article describes the basics of developing the intellectual abilities of learners based on the technologies of clarifying educational goals and turning them into tasks in the modern organization of training sessions in higher education institutions.

Keywords: Learning objective, taxonomy, identification, cognitive, psychomotor, affective, test, knowledge, understanding, application, analysis, synthesis, evaluation, method, etc.

In introducing modern pedagogical technologies into the educational process, the educator who is its administrator will be the chief guarantor of achieving the intended goal. If we look at this point of view, it is necessary to prioritize the level of training of the educator who is its administrator in the introduction of pedagogical technologies and its main basis, information and communication technology, into the educational system. Therefore, the positive or purposeful solution of most current problems of pedagogical processes on the agenda largely depends on the professional potential and pedagogical skills of the educator **Analysis of thematic literature.** As a result of research on improving the unified approach to the educational process, foreign and Uzbek scientists M.Wertheimer, CA.Thomas, D.Gordon, W.P.Bespalco, M.V.Clarin, V.Guzeev, A.N.Dixin, W.Okon, D.V.Chernilevsky, V.M.Monakhov, G.K.Selevko, M.A.Choshanov, V.Yu.Pityukov, D.G.Levites, E.S.Polat, A.A.Faktorovich, N.O.Yakovleva, G.A.Bordovsky, J.G'.Yoldashev, B.L.Farberman, N.S.Saidakhmedov, N.N.Azizhoujaeva, B.Ziyamuhammedav, A'.Q.As a result of the research of the likes of Tolipov, a pedagogical technology was created that guarantees a repeatable and final result. Its essence will consist in the accuracy of the educational goal and the fact that in order to achieve it, the learner operates independently, following a strictly defined sequence, mastering each training module. Experiments have shown that when a continuous lecture is read, learners absorb only 5 percent of the material, while in independent learning, this figure is 90 percent.

Research methodology. Today, scientific research has been carried out on methods for setting educational goals, forms of their more accurate expression, and certain experience has also been accumulated on these issues. In particular, there is a certain level of theoretical and practical information on the definition of the goals of modern training for teaching, training and the formation of the personality of the learner, as well as ways to achieve them.

In our opinion, it is impossible to look at pedagogical technology as a separate branch of pedagogical science, or as a system aimed only at optimizing educational practice. Pedagogical technology determines the areas of activity within the framework of combining theoretical and practical research in this area. The essence of the search here is the modernization based on the study of the elements that make up the pedagogical system. The reason is, the organization of any educational process reflects one or another pedagogical system. Therefore, pedagogical technology is a project of a certain pedagogical system that can be introduced into practice.

Results. In the process of training, it creates good conditions for the separation of educational, educational and developmental goals, the assimilation of knowledge and the formation of the necessary personal qualities. In the process of mastering knowledge in the training session, views and spiritual qualities are also formed, that is, the unity and interdependence of these functions is observed. Another aspect of the content of the educational function of teaching is the appropriation of educational material from Dalli. The implementation of the educational goal of teaching depends on the character of the knowledge that is given to the learner. The more accurately the educational goal is set and the more consistent it is with the educational material received in the training session, the easier it will be to choose the teaching method in the training session. The set of educational purpose of teaching also consists of a skill that is formed on the basis of the given knowledge, and the character of knowledge is determined by the corresponding skills.

The educational purpose of teaching consists in the formation of positive views and beliefs, morality, willpower and emotions in educators. The educator carries out a certain side of the educational task in the process of teaching educational material in each training session. The formation of a worldview, moral qualities of a person, emotions, volition, etc. is a continuous process, which cannot be clearly divided into limited parts. The results of the educational goal will not be as specific and accurate as the results of the educational goal. The educational goal is achieved differently in different learners. The educational purpose of the training session forms certain moral, aesthetic, emotional and volitional qualities in the person of the educator. Wrapping any educational material affects the maturation of the learner, the development of the logic of thinking in it, the forces of cognition and the motive of reading.

The implementation of the developmental goal of training is similar to the implementation of the educational goal. The most important thing in the implementation of the task of maturing, as in the implementation of the educational goal, is to form the desire of the learner to mature. In one session, it is impossible to put and implement the task of analysis, logical methods of synthesis, the development of abstract thinking skills, the formation of active and independent thoughts. The implementation of the goal of maturation of training consists in constantly planning certain ideas and developing the logic of thinking, activity and interest in knowledge. In the process of training, attention should be paid to what is set forth in the separation of educational, educational and developmental goals. Educational goals - to provide learners with knowledge, skills and qualifications in their specific system, develop them with all the necessary qualities of oral or written speech, make good use of the content of this subject so that they correctly understand the Real being, apply educational material, provide the necessary knowledge, information, skills and skills for continuing independent continuing education in the future, select educational content and structure it.

Base phrases or concepts are understood as basic information in the educational material. Base phrases also arise and are used when planning or rearranging the topic under study. The appropriation of learning material also depends largely on the appropriation of base phrases. Base phrases can also often occur on other topics of educational material. Therefore, it is convenient to study the educational material based on base phrases. Educational goals-to educate a dialectical materialistic worldview, to associate theory with practice, to interest

learning in science, to educate a culture of correct thinking, to educate human qualities such as mental, physical, moral, elegance, labor, professional education, ideological, patriotic, to be able to continue to receive knowledge independent of science.

The developing goals are the level of assimilation of theoretical knowledge in science by the learner, the development of their scientific and theoretical thinking, the result of an individual and differential approach to them, the development of human thinking, will, emotion, need, abilities, the use of scientific methods in the study of Science, the ability to apply specific methods in science. In setting the goals of education, the educator analyzes curricula, textbooks, manuals and necessary literature. Rearranges the training material. Selects the material according to the purposes of the topic. The ability of the learner takes into account the requirements of an individual approach to education. Selects theoretical and practical material suitable for the level of assimilation of Sciences.

In the U.S., England, and other nations, it is customary to set goals individually for an educator and educator. This is logical because teaching is their collaborative activity. In this, the goals are set based on the activities of the educator (such as teaching, explaining, showing, telling), while the results expressed in the character of the educator are called the tasks of Education. In this sense, educational tasks mean something that the student can know or perform at the end of the training. In order to be able to measure, determine, reproduce training, it is necessary to know the criterion for achieving each goal, that is, the educational goal should be set in such a way that it is possible to draw a clear conclusion on the Haki of achieving it. It should be noted that in the pedagogical literature, tasks are sometimes called concocted pedagogical goals.

Identifiable or identifiable learning goals are the educational goal of the learner, sometimes also called the task or issues they need to know. The question of the learner is what in education they do not know about the educational material, what should they know, how should they learn? - we tell the concept associated with the answer to the questions. Determining the purpose of an educator through educational activities is called an identifiable educational goal, which is synonymous with the purpose of the educator. The objective of an identifiable study is the unambiguous representation of the educator with the objective of the study. With the teaching goal of the educator, the learning goal of the educator is expressed in exactly equal terms but, in different ways. It is desirable that the learner's observations in the educational activities are expressed using their actions, the terms they are learning, the base phrases and concepts. In education, the specified goals of the educator (educational, educational, developmental) should be reflected in the educational goals through verbs, in the sense that they regulate the actions of the educator, clearly indicate what is being done. When studying the material, the learner must understand what the goal is. Achieving identical goals is related to the final result sought in this education.

The learner's identity goals are directly linked to his appropriation result, a goal that directly links theory to practice. The goals of the identical training come from the purpose of the educator. The learning material is broken into pieces in accordance with a few logically related small easy-to-master learners. Call this little piece the main question. The base on the topic planning is divided into several, at least two main questions, based on the phrases and concepts contained in it. General goals in the topic (educational, educational, developmental) now in each main question, in a specific case, the educational goal is determined by the educator for this question. Here, a sequence of goals is formed, which of these goals is ordered to come first, which is then. The ordering of goals is determined in connection with the fact that the general goal receives the final result. The idea of comparing goals implies that after this it is possible to observe the activities of the learner, to explain the means of measurement oracle.

Of great importance when drawing up questions that require an oral answer is the use of questions that ensure the appropriation of material at high levels of intellectuality, as well as what is being referred to as Blum questions in World pedagogy. Below we give examples of such questions: questions about cognition (factual-evidential cognition). Where, when did what happen? Where did they think? When? Questions that indicate understanding (awareness of meaning). Make a statement in your own words? Write down the detail? Which of these is a sample? Questions about application (practical significance). Where, how is it applied? Why does this happen? How can this law apply? Questions about analysis (separation of integrity into components and establishing connections between them). Compare? What are the most important features? Categorize? Questions about synthesis (generating logical new integrity from individual parts). Make a plan? How would you make it? Outline the most important aspects of the topic? Questions regarding assessment (decision making, ability to make conclusions). React to this? Is the sample in demand? Why? Which criteria can be assessed based on?

Drawing up written assignments implies the use of a variant of base words and phrases. When drawing up tasks of this form, it is also worth paying attention to the amount of tasks to be solved using interactive methods. Because the application of interactive methods such as cluster, Sink Wein, Venna diagram, Insert, conceptual table, case-staid, t-schema drawing up, technical dictation writing develops the thinking abilities of educators, ensures the assimilation of educational material at high levels of intellectuality. The fact that many developed countries using pedagogical technology are reaching a qualitatively new level of the educational process is gaining confirmation in life. The information described in this methodological manual provides the basis for thinking about the potential of pedagogical technology. Various interactive methods created within the framework of pedagogical technology provide an opportunity to take a rational and creative approach to improving the effectiveness of education, in which the teacher has his own freedom, to assess the effectiveness of various methods, tools used in the lesson himself.

The development of independent thinking and creative abilities in students is an important task not only for educators, but also for our entire society. Through knowledge, the creative activity of students, acquired skills and abilities are formed and developed, the worldview expands. To do this, the educator is obliged at the stages of the lesson, to carry out it, check it, clearly determine the goal and expected results. Effective organization of education on the basis of advanced educational technologies with a systematic approach to the educational process on the basis of the " national program of training " serves as an important factor in the training of mature personnel.

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